

Core Design of a 24-Month Cycle PWR for High-Burnup Operation Considering Full-Core Fuel Analysis

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ABSTRACT

A 24-month high-burnup fuel cycle for a large-scale PWR (pressurized water reactor) was designed and evaluated to extend the operating cycle from 18 to 24 months while maintaining safety and economic competitiveness. Core design employed the GPU-accelerated Monte Carlo code PRAGMA and the pin-wise diffusion code SPHINCS, followed by a detailed fuel performance assessment using the fuel performance code GIFT. The optimized core adopted a multi-enrichment fuel design (5.0–6.5 wt% U-235) to control power peaking. The resulting configuration achieved a maximum pin burnup of 77.5 MWd/kgU while satisfying limits on power peaking and critical boron concentration. Fuel performance analysis confirmed that key parameters—including internal pressure, cladding stress and strain, oxide thickness, and hydrogen uptake—remained within design limits. Notably, the most limiting conditions were observed not in the highest burnup pins but in those experiencing locally elevated power, highlighting the need for full-core analysis. Rod burst probability shows only a small number of rods may be susceptible under high-power conditions. Dry storage evaluations confirmed that fuel integrity can be ensured with a sufficient wet storage period prior to cask loading. Economic analysis demonstrated a 1.6% reduction in total cost due to lower O&M and capital expenses, despite higher enrichment costs. These results confirm the technical feasibility and economic benefit of the proposed 24-month high-burnup LEU+ cycle and provide a reference framework for advanced long-cycle PWR operation strategies.

Keywords: High-burnup, LEU+, full-core analysis, economic analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Extending the burnup of nuclear power plants offers significant advantages, such as reducing the amount of spent nuclear fuel and improving the overall fuel cycle economy. Accordingly, fuel burnup has been progressively increased over the past several decades. Recently, considerable efforts have been directed toward achieving a burnup level of 75,000 MWd/kgU in pressurized water reactors (PWRs) through the utilization of LEU+ (low-enriched uranium+) fuels enriched to more than 5 wt% U-235[1, 2].

However, high-burnup fuel rods require comprehensive assessment of nuclear fuel behavior, including evaluation of whether key parameters—such as rod internal pressure, cladding hoop stress, cladding hoop strain, oxide thickness, and hydrogen concentration—remain within their design limits, as well as analysis of rod burst behavior under large-break loss-of-coolant accident (LBLOCA) conditions[3]. In particular, unlike conventional PWR fuels, the risk associated with high-burnup nuclear fuel may not be directly proportional to its burnup level. For this reason, full-core fuel analysis is needed to identify the potential vulnerabilities of high burnup reactor fuel.

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In this study, a high burnup reactor core was designed to extend the fuel cycle from 18 months to 24 months at the same power level for a conventional PWR. The core was analyzed using neutronics and fuel performance codes to assess the adequacy of the design. Through iterative calculations, a core design was obtained that nearly satisfies the target burnup and the normal operating conditions for the nuclear fuel. Additional analyses, including rod burst, dry storage for spent fuel and an economic evaluation, were subsequently performed for this core.

2. Methodology

The analysis process consists of three stages: reactor design, fuel analysis, and further evaluations. The process begins with assembly design using the PRAGMA code, and the resulting assembly data are subsequently used as input for core analysis with the SPHINCS code. The core configuration is iteratively modified until the required performance criteria are satisfied. Once the core performance is achieved, the process proceeds to the fuel analysis stage using the GIFT code. If fuel performance remains within the normal operational limits, the workflow advances to the final stage, which includes safety analysis (Rod burst), dry storage analysis (GIFT & COBRA-SFS coupling) and economic evaluation (In-house developed tool). If the fuel performance does not meet the required criteria, core redesign is performed, and the cycle is repeated. The detailed descriptions of each step are as follows.

Figure 1. Framework of core design and analysis

2.1. Reactor design

The reactor design and analysis were carried out within an integrated computational framework that links the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code PRAGMA and the pin-wise, two-step reactor core analysis code SPHINCS [4]. This workflow was selected to enable pin-level core predictions (e.g., pin power/flux) for subsequent pin-resolved fuel and safety-related evaluations. Compared with assembly-wise nodal approaches requiring intra-assembly power reconstruction, the present approach directly provides pin-level quantities for downstream analyses.

PRAGMA, a GPU-accelerated Monte Carlo solver, evaluates neutron fluxes and reaction rates and generates pin-wise homogenized multigroup cross sections. Anisotropic scattering is treated using a Legendre expansion, and group-wise diffusion coefficients are computed from transport-corrected cross sections based on the standard P1 approximation, where the transport cross section is derived from the first-order scattering moment. Homogenization is intentionally performed at the pin scale to match the spatial resolution required by the downstream three-dimensional pin-resolved diffusion calculations in SPHINCS.

To mitigate potential reaction-rate and leakage inconsistencies introduced by spatial homogenization, an SPH-based equivalence treatment is applied so that the pin-level diffusion solution preserves the reference reaction-rate behavior of the heterogeneous transport solution under consistent boundary conditions. The resulting group constants are then condensed as needed and supplied to SPHINCS for three-dimensional pin-level diffusion calculations.

Using this integrated system, the reactor design procedure—from fuel assembly design to full-core configuration—was conducted for a large PWR, and the loading pattern was optimized to satisfy key performance criteria, including the core peaking factor.

2.2. Fuel analysis

The fuel analysis was conducted using the GIFT code, which is based on a two-dimensional (r - z) finite difference method[5]. GIFT incorporates a fission gas release model based on the Modified Forsberg–Massih correlation, which has been validated up to a burnup of 75,000 MWd/kgU. The code also includes a structural analysis model to evaluate pellet–cladding interaction (PCI), in which a rigid pellet model is applied once PCI occurs. With these capabilities, GIFT provides reliable predictions of high-burnup fuel behavior, demonstrating applicability to extended burnup conditions. By using the SPHINCS and GIFT codes, a straightforward one-way core-to-fuel coupling approach was applied [6]. The 3D pin-wise power history data of the quarter core calculated by SPHINCS were transferred to GIFT to perform detailed fuel performance analysis, taking into account the core loading pattern and the effects of overhaul.

2.3. Burst Analysis

The potential for rod burst was assessed based on the rod burst boundary established by the Korea Institute of Nuclear Safety [7]. This boundary determines whether rod burst occurs based on rod average burnup and peak axial power under LBLOCA conditions. There are four boundaries corresponding to burst probability levels of 1%, 5%, 10%, and 40%, respectively. Each line represents the condition under which that percentage of fuel rods is expected to burst. The rod average burnup and peak axial power were obtained from the SPHINCS and GIFT calculations, and the corresponding burst probabilities of the fuel rods were subsequently evaluated.

2.4. Dry storage analysis

Dry storage analysis was performed using the coupled GIFT and COBRA-SFS codes[8]. GIFT can evaluate spent fuel behavior under both wet and dry storage conditions, while COBRA-SFS performs thermal analysis of spent fuel in dry storage casks. The coupling enables multiphysics simulation by integrating fuel-behavior modeling and thermal evaluation. Using this approach, dry-storage fuel performance was evaluated for the pins with the highest plenum pressure and the highest burnup.

2.5. Economic analysis

Economic analysis of the designed core was conducted using an in-house–developed tool capable of calculating the LCOE (levelized cost of electricity). The tool contains capital cost, Operation & maintenance (O&M) cost, and front fuel cost of reactor. The model calculates the LCOE as the ratio of total cost to total electricity generation. The developed tool enables evaluation of cost variations in each component by accounting for changes in total power production resulting from the extended fuel cycle and higher capacity factors, as well as cost increases associated with higher fuel enrichment. Based on these results, the LCOE was determined for both the conventional PWR and the designed 24-month reactor.

3. Results

3.1. Reactor design

In the 24-month core, CE-type 16×16 fuel assemblies were designed with various U-235 enrichment levels and burnable poison loadings to control reactivity and power peaking. Seven lattice designs were developed by varying the number of burnable poison rods (0–32) and adjusting the placement of lower-enriched fuel rods, and each design was calculated for three enrichment levels of 5.5, 6.0, and 6.5 wt% U-235. Integral gadolinia burnable absorbers were incorporated by homogeneously mixing 10 wt% Gd₂O₃ into lower-enriched (4 wt% U-235) UO₂ fuel pins to suppress excess reactivity and mitigate post-

depletion local pin-power peaking relative to neighboring higher-enriched (5.5–6.5 wt%) non-Gd pins. In addition, enrichment zoning was applied to flatten the assembly power distribution by placing lower-enriched uranium near guide tubes and assembly edges and assigning even lower enrichment to the corner pins to mitigate edge effects (Figure 2(a)). The application of lower enrichment to selected fuel pins (including pins adjacent to guide tubes) also supports power peaking control after gadolinium depletion, mitigating local power increases once the Gd burnable absorber is consumed.

The core adopts a low-leakage loading pattern, placing fresh fuel in the interior and twice-burned assemblies at the periphery (Figure 2(b)). In Figure 2, each color indicates the burnup state of the assemblies (fresh, once-burned, or twice-burned), and the numbers denote the highest enrichment in each assembly. In Figure 2(b), black and red arrows are added to indicate the typical movement paths of assemblies between cycles (from the first to the second cycle, and from the second to the third cycle, respectively). Although only a quarter-core is shown, the actual transfer includes assemblies coming from the opposite quarter-core at the corresponding relative positions, which should be noted when interpreting the shuffling paths. The core design was performed under constraints on cladding hoop stress and internal gas pressure, consistent with the criteria described in Section 2.2 (Fuel Analysis). The peaking factors (FXY and F_q) of the 24-month core are higher than those of a conventional PWR; however, F_q still satisfies the limit of 2.45 specified in the conventional PWR Final Safety Analysis Report (Figure 3(a)–(b)). Other indicators (e.g., FXY and ASI) may show higher values than those of the conventional/18-month core, but they remain within a range that can be addressed through additional optimization of fuel management and enrichment/poison zoning. Although the axial shape index (ASI) of the 24-month core exhibits a larger absolute value than that of the 18-month core (Figure 3(c)), positive ASI is generally of greater concern than negative ASI in safety analyses. Therefore, these results are considered acceptable.

Figure 2. Core design for 24-month core; (a) Example of desinged assembly, (b) core loading pattern in quarter core

Figure 3. Core peaking factor comparison between 24-month core and 18-month core

A detailed comparison of the core performance parameters between the 24-month and 18-month cores is presented in Table I. To enhance oxidation resistance, the cladding material was changed to PRXA.

The cycle batch number was reduced from 2.51 to 2.30 to limit the maximum fuel burnup within the core. The maximum pin burnup of the 24-month core reached 77.5 MWd/kgU (S 14 assembly), slightly exceeding the design target of 75 MWd/kgU. To control the internal rod pressure, the plenum length was increased to enlarge the free volume, which is effective in mitigating excessive pressure increase. Accordingly, the active fuel length decreased by 1.5%, while the average LHGR (linear heat generation rate) increased by 1.5%, reaching 18.66 kW/m. In addition, the peak CBC (critical boron concentration) increased to 1634 ppm due to the higher enrichment of the fuel.

Table I. 24-month core and 18-month core comparison

Features	Conventional	24-month
U235 Enrichment [w/o]	4.5	5.5-6.5
Cladding material	CWSR	PRXA
Cycle length [EFPD] / Batch	478/2.51	700/2.30
Avg (max) pin burnup [MWD/kgU]	49.2 (61.1)	63.2 (77.5)
Active fuel length [m/inch]	3.81/150	3.75/147.638
Avg LHGR [kW/m]/[kW/ft]	18.37/5.60	18.66/5.69
Peak CBC (ppm)	1204	1634

3.2. Fuel performance

Figure 3 shows the behavior of various fuel performance parameters, where each point represents an individual fuel rod characterized by its discharge burnup and the corresponding maximum parameter value during operation. All fuel rods in the reactor exhibited internal pressures below 15.5 MPa, which corresponds to the system operating pressure and serves as the design limit to prevent outward cladding creep and ensure fuel integrity (Figure 4(a)). Notably, the maximum rod internal pressure does not occur in the thrice burned, highest burnup pin, but rather in a centrally located pin in the L11 assembly with a moderately high burnup level. This phenomenon results from the increased fission gas release rate under conditions of concurrently high linear power and burnup, indicating that core design must consider both parameters instead of focusing solely on maximum burnup. In addition, the fuel rods with the highest internal pressures within an assembly were typically located near guide tubes or at corner positions, suggesting that additional safety margins can be secured by tuning the fuel pin arrangement within each assembly.

The calculated pellet centerline temperature remains well below the fuel melting point of 2865 °C (Figure 4(b)). Although burnable poison has relatively low thermal conductivity, its lower local heat generation ensures sufficient thermal margins. A sharp increase in hoop stress, which momentarily exceeds 300 MPa, is observed in some fuel rods during reactor startup (Figure 4(c)), primarily due to PCI caused by the thermal expansion mismatch between the pellet and the cladding materials. Such stress occurs in fuel rods that experience a significant power increase before and after overhaul under high burnup conditions, for example in assemblies relocated from M2 to J17 after overhaul. This rapid stress increase occurs only for a short period, so the transient stress exceeding 300 MPa does not induce fuel failure. However, this finding suggests that, in high burnup cores, attention should be paid to parameters such as the heating rate during reactor startup and local power distribution to mitigate mechanical stress. The hoop strain remains well within the design limit of 1 percent throughout the entire operating period, providing adequate mechanical margin (Figure 4(d)).

The oxide layer thickness remains low due to the excellent corrosion resistance of the PRXA cladding. Even after three operating cycles, the maximum oxide thickness is maintained at approximately 20

micrometers (Figure 4 (e)). In addition, the hydrogen concentration in the cladding remains sufficiently low, below 120 ppm, further confirming its resistance to corrosion and hydriding (Figure 4(f)).

Figure 4. Fuel performance of 24-month core; (a) Rod internal pressure, (b) Maximum pellet centerline temperature, (c) Maximum cladding hoop stress, (d) Maximum cladding hoop strain, (e) Maximum oxide thickness, (f) Maximum hydrogen concentration

3.3. Burst rod analysis

Rod burst occurs most frequently at the beginning of the cycle (BOC) and around the middle of the cycle (MOC), when the power-peaking factor (F_q) reaches its maximum. Rod positions with a burst probability greater than 1% are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 (a) shows the rod burst map at 200 days, and Figure 5 (b) shows the map at 600 days. It can be observed that a greater number of rod bursts are predicted at 600 days, when both the burnup and the power-peaking factor are higher. In addition, most rod bursts occur during the first cycle, which is attributed to the lower power levels in the subsequent cycles. This indicates that the number of rods burst pins is more strongly influenced by the maximum power rather than by burnup. It also implies that most bursts occur before the stage in which fragmentation becomes severe and strong fuel dispersal takes place.

Figure 5. Rod burst map of 24-month core; (a) 200 day, (b) 600 day

3.4. Dry storage analysis

High burnup and elevated internal pressure significantly influence cladding temperature, hoop stress, and strain behavior during dry storage. The pin with the maximum burnup (77 MWd/kgU, 9.8 MPa internal pressure) and the pin with the maximum internal pressure (68 MWd/kgU, 14.1 MPa internal pressure) were selected to evaluate fuel integrity during dry storage. Figure 5 presents cladding peak temperature, cladding hoop stress, and cladding hoop creep strain; the red reference lines indicate NRC guidelines (current: 400 °C for temperature and 90 MPa for hoop stress, and historical: 1% for hoop creep strain). The green line shows the conventional PWR reference at 60 MWd/kgU with 4.5 years of wet storage. For cladding temperature, all cases remain below the NRC limit of 400 °C, except for the

maximum-burnup pin after 6 years of wet storage. The overall temperature behavior is similar to or lower than that of conventional PWR fuel.

For cladding hoop stress, all evaluated cases satisfy the 90 MPa limit, but stresses are substantially higher than the conventional reference, reducing the margin to the guideline. It should also be noted that PRXA cladding can experience radial hydride formation (RHF) even below 90 MPa, which should be considered in high-burnup dry storage evaluations. For cladding hoop creep strain, both selected pins remain at or below 1% in all cases except the 6-year wet storage condition, which follows the same trend as temperature. These results indicate that ensuring a sufficient wet storage period prior to cask loading is important for maintaining fuel integrity, while highlighting reduced stress margins relative to conventional PWR fuel. This also suggests that, as wet storage duration increases for high-burnup operation, the required wet storage capacity might need to be expanded accordingly.

Figure 6. Dry storage analysis of peak rod internal pressure and peak burnup pin; (a) Cladding peak temperature, (b) Max cladding hoop stress, (c) Cladding hoop creep strain

3.5. Economic analysis

The economic impact of extending the fuel cycle can be assessed from two aspects: an increase in fuel cost due to higher enrichment, and a reduction in total cost resulting from decreased O&M expenses and an increased capacity factor. A comprehensive cost evaluation of the reactor core requires consideration of both cost components. According to the in-house developed tool, both the capital cost and the O&M cost decrease by 2.5%, while the front-end fuel cost increases by 9.5%. Considering these effects, the total cost of the 24-month core is expected to decrease by approximately 1.6%, since the capital and O&M costs account for a much larger portion of the overall cost than the fuel cost (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Cost evaluation of 18-month and 24-month core

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study developed and evaluated a 24-month high-burnup fuel cycle for a large PWR to extend the conventional 18-month cycle while maintaining safety and economic competitiveness. The integrated PRAGMA-SPHINCS-GIFT analysis framework enabled detailed neutronic and fuel performance assessments for the proposed core.

The optimized loading pattern, employing multi-enrichment LEU+ fuel, achieved a cycle length of 700 EFPD with acceptable power-peaking factors and critical boron concentration. Fuel performance evaluations confirmed that key safety parameters—such as internal pressure, pellet centerline temperature, cladding hoop stress and strain, oxide thickness, and hydrogen concentration—remained well within design limits. Notably, the most limiting conditions for rod internal pressure and hoop stress were not associated with the highest-burnup pins, but rather with fuel rods subjected to sustained high power or large power variations at high burnup, indicating that comprehensive full-core analysis is essential for reliable high-burnup core design.

Rod burst analysis showed that most potential bursts occur near the beginning and middle of the cycle, when the power-peaking factor (F_q) reaches its maximum. These bursts predominantly appear in fresh fuel assemblies due to their inherently higher local power levels. Dry storage evaluation further confirmed that both the maximum burnup pin and the maximum internal pressure pin maintain acceptable fuel integrity when a sufficient wet storage period is provided prior to cask loading. Economic assessment demonstrated a total core cost reduction of approximately 1.6% compared to the reference 18-month cycle, despite increased enrichment costs. These results verify the technical feasibility and economic advantage of the proposed 24-month high-burnup LEU+ cycle and provide a valuable reference framework for the development of advanced long-cycle PWR operation strategies.

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